

Centrolepidosporium sclerodermum, gen. et sp. nov. (*Ustilaginomycetes*) from Australia

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Abstract. A new genus, *Centrolepidosporium*, is proposed to accommodate a new smut fungus, *C. sclerodermum*, collected in Australia on *Centrolepis exserta*. The new species is unique in that it produces tightly packed spores in spore balls surrounded by a cortex of sterile cells. This is the first report of a smut fungus on the plant family *Centrolepidaceae*.

Key words: new species, smut fungi, *Sporisorium*, *Tilletia*, *Tranzscheliella*, *Urocystis*, *Ustilaginomycetes*

Introduction

The *Centrolepidaceae* is a family of 3 genera (*Aphelia*, *Centrolepis* and *Gaimardia*) and about 36 species (Mabberley 1998), mostly occurring in Australia but also found in New Zealand, throughout south-east Asia to Laos with an outlying *Gaimardia* species in South America (Cooke 1988). It is a family of small, sedge-like annuals and perennials with greatly reduced unisexual flowers combined into a pseudanthium, which is a highly condensed unit inflorescence analogous to a bisexual flower but composed of 2-many reduced unisexual flowers (Cooke 1988). DNA sequence analysis has shown that the *Centrolepidaceae* represents a clade nested within the family *Restionaceae* (Bremer 2002). The *Centrolepidaceae* is represented in Australia by all genera and 29 species (Cooke 2006).

In the *Restionaceae*, 21 species of smut fungi in 2 genera (*Restiosporium* and *Websdanea*) are known (Vánky 2006). Smut fungi have not been previously reported on the *Centrolepidaceae*. Recently, a smut fungus was discovered in

the Northern Territory, Australia, on *Centrolepis exserta* (R. Br.) Roem. & Schult., which grows across northern Australia on the margins of streams and wetlands, and moist sites in woodland or grassland, mainly on sandy alluvial soils (Cooke 1992). This collection represents both a new species and also a new genus (comp. Vánky 2002).

Materials and Methods

Sorus and spore characteristics were studied using dried herbarium specimens. For light microscopy (LM), spores were dispersed in a droplet of lactic acid on a microscope slide, covered with a cover glass, followed by gently heating to boiling point to rehydrate the spores, and examined at 1000× magnification. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), dry spore balls (partly squashed), or dry spores were placed on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, c. 20 nm, and examined in a SEM at 10 kV.

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Taxonomy

Centrolepidosporium R.G. Shivas & Vánky, gen. nov.

Sori in fructibus plantarum familiae *Centrolepidaceae*, semina massa nigra, granulopulverea glomerulorum sporarum substituentes; peridium, columella et cellulae steriles absentes. *Glomeruli sporarum pigmentiferi (brunnei)*, permanentes, e massa centrali sporarum et e cortice cellularum fungalium sterilium eam circumdante compositi. *Germinatio sporarum cum hyphis ramosis in ipsis basidiosporis ad sterigmata formatis.*

Typus generis C. sclerodermum.

Sori in the fruits of plants in the *Centrolepidaceae*, replacing the seeds with a black, granular-powdery mass of spore balls; peridium, columella, and sterile cells are lacking. **Spore balls** pigmented (brown), permanent, composed of a central mass of spores surrounded by a cortex of sterile fungal cells. **Spore germination** results in branched hyphae on which basidiospores are formed on sterigmata.

Type of the genus:

Centrolepidosporium sclerodermum R.G. Shivas & Vánky, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice Centrolepis exserta (R. Br.) Roem. & Schult. (fide W.K. Harris, BRI), Australia, Northern Territory, 100 km SW oppid. Jabiru, 10.VI.2006, leg. M.J. Ryley, M.D.E. & R.G. Shivas. *Holotypus* in BRIP 48 117; *isotypus* in Herbario Ustilag. Vánky, HUV 21 360.

Sori in fructibus (= folliculis) omnibus inflorescentiae eiusdem, bracteis duobus inflorescentiae condensatae occulti, semina destruentes et folliculos glomerulis sporarum implentes. In maturitate folliculi longitudinaliter disrupti massam glomerulorum sporarum nigram, primo agglutinatam postea granulopulveream ostendentes. Infectio systemica: folliculi omnes inflorescentiae et inflorescentiae omnes plantae eiusdem infectae. **Glomeruli sporarum globosi, subglobosi, ovoidei, ellipsoidales vel parum irregulares, cum lateribus 1-2 aliquantum depressis, 40-70 (-80) × 35-60 μm, atro-rubrobrunnei, opaci, e sporis multis (pluries decem vel centum?) arcte compactis, cortice cellularum sterilium circumdatis. Sporae rotundato-subpolyedricae vel polyedricae propter compactionem, 6-9 × 5,5-7 μm, pallide flavido-olivaceobrunneae; pariete tenui, cca. 0,5 μm, levi. Cortex 3-4 μm crasso, atro-rubrobrunneus, e cellulis fungalibus sterilibus firmiter agglutinatis, tangentialiter depressis, polygonaliter irregularibus, in diametro 2-10 μm, superficie libera irregulariter crenatis, in visu laterali imagine obliqua irregulariter asperis compositus. Pressu valido cortice rupto sporae conspicuae. Germinatio sporarum**

hyphis ramosis basidiosporas producentibus. Basidiosporae cylindricae, ellipsoidales usque fusiformes, 4-18 × 1-1,5 (-2) μm, in sterigmatibus lateralibus et terminalibus, sporae etiam secundariae et tertiariae in catenis productae.

Sori (Figs 1-2) in all fruits (= follicles) of an inflorescence, hidden by the two bracts of the condensed inflorescence, destroying the seeds and filling the follicles with spore balls. At maturity, the follicles split longitudinally, disclosing the black, at first agglutinated, later granular-powdery mass of spore balls. Infection systemic, all follicles of an inflorescence and all inflorescences of a plant are infected. **Spore balls** (Figs 3-7) globose, subglobose, ovoid, ellipsoidal or slightly irregular, with 1-2 somewhat flattened sides, 40-70 (-80) × 35-60 μm, dark reddish brown, opaque, composed of a great number (several tens or one hundred?) of tightly packed spores surrounded by a cortex of sterile cells. **Spores** (Fig. 6) rounded subpolyhedrally or polyhedrally irregular from compaction, 6-9 × 5.5-7 μm, pale yellowish or olivaceous brown; wall thin, c. 0.5 μm, smooth. **Cortex** (Fig. 6) 3-4 μm thick, dark reddish brown, composed of firmly agglutinated, tangentially flattened, polygonally irregular sterile fungal cells, 2-10 μm in diameter, free surface irregularly crenate, in side view the profile is irregularly rough. By hard pressure the cortex ruptures and the spores became evident. **Spore germination** (on water agar, at room temp., in 2 days, Fig. 8) resulted in branched hyphae from which basidiospores are formed. **Basidiospores** cylindrical, ellipsoidal to fusiform, measuring 4-18 × 1-1.5 (-2) μm, producing secondary and tertiary spores in chains, on terminal and lateral sterigmata.

On *Centrolepidaceae: Centrolepis exserta* (R. Br.) Roem. & Schult.

Distribution: Australia. Known only from the type locality.

Etymology: *Centrolepidosporium* derived from the name of the host family *Centrolepidaceae* and *-sporum*, which is the ending for many genera of smut fungi that form spore balls; *sclerodermum* from the Greek *scleros* = dry, hard, and *derm(at-)* = skin, integument, referring to the cortex of the spore balls.

The spore balls are formed within a hyaline mass of concentrically arranged sporogenous hyphae, in which groups of hyphae with slightly swollen tips appear. These spore ball initials, measuring c. 20 μm in diam, increase in size, become slightly yellowish, with a central mass of globose young spores and a peripheral, thin, darker, tangentially flattened cortical layer. By maturation the young spore balls have increased in size and become darkly pigmented, whereas the surrounding hyaline mass of sporogenous hyphae disappears.

Figs 1-7. *Centrolepidosporium sclerodermum* on *Centrolepis exserta*. **Fig. 1.** Habit (type). Bar = 2 cm. **Fig. 2.** An inflorescence of *Centrolepis exserta* with fruits (follicles) filled with spore balls of *C. sclerodermum* (type). Bar = 1 mm. **Fig. 3.** A broken follicle of *Centrolepis exserta* filled with mature spore balls of *C. sclerodermum*, and some free spore balls. Bar = 100 μm. **Figs 4-5.** Spore ball building of *C. sclerodermum*. **4.** Globoid, concentrically arranged sporogenous hyphae within a hyaline matrix of hyphae. In the lower middle, a young spore ball can be seen with spore initials surrounded by a hyaline cortex. **5.** Spore balls in different stages of maturation. Bars = 10 μm. **Fig. 6.** A broken spore ball showing a few tightly packed spores surrounded by a dark reddish brown cortex. Bar = 10 μm. **Fig. 7.** Spore balls in SEM. Bar = 10 μm

Fig. 8. Branched hyphae of *Centrolepidosporium sclerodermum* (type) resulted from spore germination. On the hyphae basidiospores are formed on sterigmata (arrows) producing secondary and tertiary spores in chains. Bar = 10 μ m

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